

COMPOSITE STRUCTURES WITH BUILT-IN DIAGNOSTICS

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SUMMARY :

A built-in diagnostic technique based on a distributed sensor network is presented for composite structures. The technique uses the built-in sensors to measure the response of the structures and process the measured signals to interpret the changes of signals at two different times in terms of physical change of the structures. The development of the technique includes three major items: sensor selection, sensor/structure integration, and signal processing and interpretation.

Piezoelectric materials were selected for the technique as sensors for receiving information as well as actuators for generating diagnostic signals. A SMART (Stanford Multi-Actuator Receiver Transduction) Layer Technology has been developed for fabricating a network of distributed piezoelectric elements for both embedding in and surface-mounting on composite structures. Application software has also been developed for the SMART layer to identify impact load in real time and to detect impact damage automatically in composite panels. A prototype of the proposed technique has been developed and successfully applied to composite plates and stiffened panels.

KEYWORDS : Smart Structures, Structural Health Monitoring, carbon-matrix composites, composite structures.

I. INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are susceptible to damage which can be induced by service loads and accidental impact. Early detection of such damage is critical for maintaining the integrity of structures in use. Unfortunately, current composite structure inspection techniques are time consuming, labor intensive, and expensive, which significantly increases the overhead cost associated with the use of these structures. Current available techniques include coin tapping, X-ray, and ultrasound – all of which require the structure to be taken out of service and often disassembled. This approach is uneconomical and sometimes impossible to implement (e.g., space structures).

Recent advances in smart structure technology have led to the development of new structural diagnostic techniques for monitoring of structural condition and detection of damage while the structures are still in service [1-5]. The techniques use advanced sensors built into the structures to measure structural response in real time and interpret the sensor measurements in terms of

physical changes in structural condition. The potential direct benefits from the new technology include:

- Real-time monitoring and reporting – saving in maintenance cost
- Minimum human involvement – reduce labor, downtime, and human error
- Automation – improve safety and reliability

Basically, there are three key developments that are critical for the techniques: sensor selection, sensor/ integration, signal processing and interpretation. This paper will present a summary of the built-in diagnostic technique based on the SMART layer technology [6-11] for composite structures.

II. BUILT-IN STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING

In general, a built-in diagnostic system shall consist of a built-in network of sensors for collecting sensor measurements and software for interpreting the sensor measurements in terms of the physical conditions of the structures (Figure 1).

Figure 1 The Proposed Built-in Structural Health Monitoring System.

Accordingly, the development of the proposed structural health monitoring system can be categorized into two areas: hardware, which includes integrated sensor/structure network and signal input and output, and software, which includes signal processing and interpretation (Figure 2).

STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING SYSTEM

Figure 2 Components of the proposed Structural Health Monitoring System

III. HARDWARE DEVELOPMENT

3.1 SMART Layer Approach

Although there are many types of sensors available, implementing a large network of sensor on a new or existing structure poses a major challenge for developing a practical monitoring system. The sensor network must be easily and reliably integrated with the host structures, require minimal labor and produce minimal or no effect on the integrity of the structures.

A method has been developed to implement a network of distributed piezoelectric sensors/actuators into composite structures [6]. This method is based on the flexible circuit printing technique, which is commonly used in the electronic industry. The fabricated thin, flexible sheet supporting a network of actuators/sensors is referred to as a SMART (Stanford Multi-Actuator-Receiver Transduction) Layer (Figure 3).

Stanford Multi-Actuator Receiver Transduction Layer (SMART Layer)

□ FLEXIBLE PRINTED CIRCUIT TECHNIQUE

Figure 3 Schematic description of the SMART layer

The SMART layer is made of a thermoplastic dielectric film with a distributed network of piezoelectric disks serving as both sensors and actuators. The thickness of the film is about 0.002 inch. Piezoelectric ceramic (PZT) was selected to form the sensor network, and the size of the piezoelectric elements can be chosen at the discretion of the users. For the current design, a 0.25" diameter 0.01" thick disk was used. The pattern of the piezoceramic network and the distance between the piezoelectric disks can be designed to suit the specific application.

The major processing steps of manufacturing the SMART layer involve printing and etching a conductor pattern onto a dielectric substrate, laminating a dielectric cover layer for electrical insulation, and mounting the array of piezoceramics on the circuit. For laminated composites, the SMART layer can be considered as an extra ply laid down between composite plies or patched on the surfaces of the laminates during lay-up. After co-cure, the resulting composite laminates would have an integrated network of active piezoelectric elements that can be used to send and receive diagnostic signals within the composite structures.

The SMART layer design has been demonstrated [6-8] that 1) the layer can withstand typical composite cure temperatures (350°F), 2) the layer can provide adequate electric insulation for the embedded wires and devices, and 3) the layer has minimal effect on the integrity of the host structure if it is embedded inside a composite material.

Several SMART Layer prototypes have been successfully fabricated and integrated onto composite structures. Figure 4 shows a photograph of a SMART layer which is 30 inches by 36

inches (left) and a composite plate with the SMART layer embedded (right). Tests have shown that the piezoelectric actuators and sensors in the layer provided consistent and uniform responses over a period of time and for a wide range of frequencies. The signals obtained showed good consistency and repeatability.

Figure 4 (Left) A SMART layer with an embedded network of thirteen distributed piezo-sensors and actuators. (Right) A 36'' by 30'' composite plate with an embedded SMART layer.

3.2 Signal Input/Output Hardware

With the sensor network integrated with the host structure, the built-in piezoelectric elements in the SMART layer could be used as sensors to record dynamic response of the structure in real time and as actuators to generate diagnostic signals within the structure. In order to provide such a dual functionality, a system to control and communicate with SMART layers has to be developed as shown in Figure 5. The system hardware would include a signal receiver to receive sensor measurements, a signal generator for generating diagnostic signals for actuators, and a processor for controlling the diagnostic signal generation and for data processing and interpretation.

Figure 5 Schematic of the hardware system

Once the SMART layer is integrated with the structure, it can retrieve information that are associated with the environmental or physical changes in the structural condition. The SMART layer can function as a passive or an active diagnostic system, depending on the usage of the piezoelectric elements. To use as a passive diagnostic system, the piezoelectric elements are used as sensors to measure the strain values of the structure. To use as an active diagnostic system, one piezo-element is used as an actuator to input a diagnostic signal while another piezo-element is used to retrieve the diagnostic signal. The role of each piezo-element can be reversed to work either as an actuator or a sensor, forming multiple combinations of actuator-sensor pairs. In both cases, the information retrieved from the structure can be used to infer the health of the structure.

The information retrieved by the SMART layer can be used to assess the health condition of the structure in many ways. In each diagnostic technique, the retrieved information has to go through a series of signal processing and interpretation before meaningful information about the structure's condition can be extracted. This series of information processing is handled by software stored in the computer to perform a specific application. The robustness of any diagnostic technique relies strongly on the accuracy and reliability of the application software.

IV. SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT

Several application software are being developed for the SMART layer at Stanford, which include: 1) Identification of an unknown impact load 2) Estimation of the impact damage 3) Monitoring the cure condition of composites.

Impact Identification

When an impact occurs on a composite plate with an embedded SMART layer, the response of the structure is captured by the SMART layer. The piezo sensors on the SMART layer measure the instantaneous strains of the plate caused by the impact loading. Figure 6 shows the strain values of the plate recorded by five piezo sensors over the duration of the impact.

Based on the sensor measurement, software has been developed to identify the location and the force-time history of the impact on composite panels with and without stiffeners. The application software has been shown to be very robust in identifying unknown external impacts [9,10].

Figure 6 Example of passive sensing diagnostic: Identification of the location and force-time history of an external impact.

Figure 7 shows a typical configuration of the composite stiffened panels that were studied. The panels were fabricated at Boeing Commercial Airplane Company and SMART layers were surface-mounted on the back surface of the panels at Stanford. Figure 8 presents the comparison between the impact force-time history between the data and the prediction from the software. The data was taken from a transducer mounted on an hammer.

Figure 7 the geometry of the composite stiffened panels considered in the study.

Figure 8 Comparison of impact force-time history between the measured data and the predictions from the software for a stiffened composite panel [10].

Damage Detection

With the SMART layer, pre-selected diagnostic signals can be generated to inspect damage inside structures. The built-in piezo-element can be used as an actuator to send out propagating signals that can be measured by nearby piezo sensors in the structure. Before the introduction of damage, the signal can be stored as healthy reference data (case A). After damage, the propagating signals may be affected due to the existence of the damage (case B). The difference

in the signals before and after the introduction of damage contains information about the damage.

Figure 9 Example of active sensing diagnostics: Detection of the size and location of an internal damage.

By interpreting the change in the propagating signals, software is being developed to infer the location and the extent of the damage in composite plates containing a built-in piezoelectric sensor/actuator network [11,12]. Extensive experiments are being conducted to validate the software [12]. Figure 10 shows the comparison of location and size of impact damage in a composite plate between the prediction of the software and the actual data. The image of the impact damage is shown in the X-radiograph of Figure 10.

Figure 10 (Right) X-Radiograph of an impact damage image and four piezo-elements. (Left) Comparison of predicted and actual impact damage location and size.

Cure Monitoring

During autoclave curing of composites, the composite material undergoes dramatic change in material properties. Since material properties strongly affect the propagation of the diagnostic signals inside the structure, the progress of the cure can be monitored by comparing the received diagnostic signal at different times.

Figure 11 (left) shows the monitoring setup which consists of a composite part embedded with a SMART layer curing inside an autoclave. A piezo-disk is used to send out a diagnostic signal while another piezo-disk is used to retrieve it. Experimental data has shown that the change in the phase of the diagnostic signals is very sensitive to the curing progress (Figure 11 right); hence, by measuring the phase change of the received diagnostic signals at different times over the cure cycle, the complete cure cycle can be monitored. Software has been developed to automatically monitor the progress of the composite cure based on phase shift [8].

Figure 11 Example of active sensing diagnostic: Process monitoring of curing composite inside an autoclave.

VI. CONCLUSION

A structural health monitoring technique based on the SMART layer technology is being developed for composite structures. The SMART layer has been demonstrated to be an effective and reliable method for integrating sensors with composite structures. Multiple applications are being pursued by using the technology. Computer software has been developed for the SMART layer to identify impact load and to detect impact damage in composite structures. It has also demonstrated the applicability of the SMART layer to monitor the cure condition of composites.

VII. REFERENCES

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